

ON THE EXISTENCE OF MINIMIZERS IN SHALLOW RESIDUAL RELU NEURAL NETWORK OPTIMIZATION LANDSCAPES

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ABSTRACT. In this article, we show existence of minimizers in the loss landscape for residual artificial neural networks (ANNs) with multi-dimensional input layer and one hidden layer with ReLU activation. Our work contrasts earlier results in [GJL22] and [PRV21] which showed that in many situations minimizers do not exist for common smooth activation functions even in the case where the target functions are polynomials. The proof of the existence property makes use of a closure of the search space containing all functions generated by ANNs and additional discontinuous *generalized responses*. As we will show, the additional generalized responses in this larger space are suboptimal so that the minimum is attained in the original function class.

1. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning methods – often consisting of *artificial neural networks* (ANNs) trained through *gradient descent* (GD) type optimization methods – are nowadays omnipresent computational methods which are heavily employed in many industrial applications as well as scientific research activities. Despite the mind-blowing success of such computational schemes, in general, it remains an open problem of research to rigorously prove (or disprove) the convergence of GD optimization methods in the training of ANNs. Even in the situation of shallow ANNs with just one hidden layer it remains an open research question whether GD methods do converge to a stationary point in the training of such ANNs.

In the literature regarding the training of ANNs there are, however, several partial error analysis results for GD type optimization methods (by which we mean, everything, time-continuous gradient flow processes, deterministic GD optimization methods, as well as stochastic GD optimization methods), see Section 2. Many convergence results assume that the considered GD type optimization process is (almost surely) bounded, loosely speaking, in the sense that

$$(1) \quad \sup_{t \in [0, \infty)} \|\Theta_t\| < \infty$$

where $\Theta: [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\mathfrak{d}}$ corresponds to the employed GD type optimization process (which could be a gradient flow optimization process or a time-continuous version of a discrete GD type optimization process), where $\mathfrak{d} \in \mathbb{N}$ corresponds to the number of trainable parameters, and where $\|\cdot\|$ refers to the standard norm on $\mathbb{R}^{\mathfrak{d}}$.

In general, it remains an open problem to verify (1) (and, thus, whether the many achievements concerning the convergence of GD are actually applicable in context of the training of ANNs). The question whether (1) is satisfied seems to be closely related to *the existence of minimizers in the optimization landscape*; cf. [GJL22, PRV21]. In particular, in [GJL22] counterexamples to (1) are given and *divergence* of GD type optimization processes is proved in the sense that

$$(2) \quad \liminf_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|\Theta_t\| = \infty$$

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in certain cases where there do not exist minimizers in the optimization landscape. A divergence phenomenon of the form (2) may *slow down* (or even completely rule out) the convergence of the error function, which is the highly relevant quantity in practical applications. In this aspect, it seems to be strongly advisable to *design the ANN architecture* in a way so that there exist minimizers in the optimization landscape and so that the divergence in (2) *fails to happen*.

Overparametrized networks in the setting of empirical risk minimization (more ReLU neurons than data points to fit) are able to perfectly interpolate the data (cf. [Fou22, Lemma 27.3]) such that there exists a network configuration achieving zero error and, thus, a global minimum in the search space. For shallow feedforward ANNs using ReLU activation it has been shown that also in the underparametrized regime there exists a global minimum if the ANN has a one-dimensional output [LRG24], whereas there are pathological counterexamples in higher dimensions [LMQ22].

However, for general measures μ not necessarily consisting of a finite number of Dirac measures the literature on the existence of global minima is very limited. The question whether there exist minimizers in the optimization landscape seems to be closely related to the choice of the *activation function* and the specific architecture of the ANN. Indeed, in the case of *fully-connected feedforward ANNs with just one hidden layer and one-dimensional input and output layer*, on the one hand for several common (smooth) activations such as

- the *standard logistic activation*,
- the *softplus activation*,
- the *inverse tangent (arctan) activation*,
- the *hyperbolic tangent activation*, and
- the *softsign activation*

it has been shown (cf. [GJL22, Theorems 1.3 and 1.4] and [PRV21, Section 1.2]) that, in general, there *do not exist minimizers in the optimization landscape* even if the class of considered target functions is restricted to smooth functions or even polynomials but, on the other hand for the *ReLU activation*, it has been proved in [JR22, Theorem 1.1] that for every Lipschitz continuous target function there *do exist minimizers in the optimization landscape*. These existence/non-existence phenomena for minimizers in the optimization landscape thus reveal a *fundamental difference* of the ReLU activation compared to the above mentioned smooth activations. This might give a partial explanation for why the ReLU activation seems to outperform other smooth activations in many regression tasks using a convex loss function, even though it fails to be differentiable in contrast to the above mentioned continuously differentiable activation functions.

Theorem 1.1 in [JR22] is, however, restricted to Lipschitz continuous target functions, to the *standard mean square loss*, and to ANNs with one neuron on the input layer. ANNs with multi-dimensional input layer are not considered. In this work, we show existence for *shallow residual ANNs with multi-dimensional input, general continuous target functions, and general strictly convex loss functions*. As activation function we consider the *ReLU activation* $\mathbb{R} \ni x \mapsto \max\{x, 0\} = x^+ \in \mathbb{R}$. Interestingly, the multi-dimensionality has a significant impact on the problem. It induces an additional geometric assumption that has not appeared in the one-dimensional setting. This assumption is not an artifact of our approach, but a general prerequisite for the existence of minimizers. We provide a counterexample where the respective assumption is not satisfied and where no minimizers exist, see Example 4.4.

We provide the main existence result of our work in two versions. Theorem 1.2 is the most general version. A slightly more restrictive but more intuitive version is Theorem 1.1 below. There, we restrict to L^p -loss and work with a simpler geometric assumption compared with the general version.

Let us now formally introduce shallow residual ANNs with $d_{\text{in}} \in \mathbb{N}$ neurons on the input layer (d_{in} being fixed throughout the article) and $d \in \mathbb{N}_0$ neurons on the hidden layer. These can be parametrized by elements

$$(3) \quad \mathbb{W} = (W^1, W^2, b) \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}} \times (d+1)} \times \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^{d+1} =: \mathcal{W}_d,$$

where we enumerate the elements of the matrix and vectors as

$$(4) \quad W^1 = (w_{i,j}^1)_{i=1,\dots,d_{\text{in}},j=0,\dots,d}, \quad W^2 = (w_j^2)_{j=1,\dots,d} \quad \text{and} \quad b = (b_j)_{j=0,\dots,d}.$$

Moreover, for every $j \in \{0, 1, \dots, d\}$ we write $w_j^1 = (w_{i,j}^1)_{i=1,\dots,d_{\text{in}}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$. We call \mathbb{W} a *network configuration* and \mathcal{W}_d the *parametrization class*. We often refer to a configuration of a neural network as the (*neural*) *network* \mathbb{W} . A configuration $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ is associated with the function $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ given by

$$(5) \quad \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x) = w_0^1 \cdot x + b_0 + \sum_{j=1}^d w_j^2 (w_j^1 \cdot x + b_j)^+,$$

where \cdot denotes the scalar product. We call $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}$ *realization function* or *response* of the network \mathbb{W} . Note that in general the response of a network is a continuous and piecewise affine function from $\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ to \mathbb{R} . We conceive $\mathbb{W} \mapsto \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}$ as a parametrization of a class of potential response functions $\{\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}: \mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d\}$ in a minimization problem.

Intuitively, W^1 describes the linear part (*weight matrix*) in the affine transformation from the d_{in} -dimensional input layer to the d -dimensional hidden layer as well as in the skip connection, W^2 describe the linear part (weight matrix) in the affine transformation from the d -dimensional hidden layer to the 1-dimensional output layer and b describes the additive part (*bias vector*) in the affine transformation from the d_{in} -dimensional input layer to the d -dimensional hidden layer as well as in the skip connection.

It follows the simple version of our existence result.

Theorem 1.1 (Existence of minimizer – residual ANNs). *Let $p \in (1, \infty)$, $d_{\text{in}} \in \mathbb{N}$, $d \in \mathbb{N}_0$, let $f: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $h: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be continuous, assume that $h^{-1}((0, \infty))$ is a bounded and convex set, and let $\text{err}^p: \mathcal{W}_d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfy for all $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ that*

$$(6) \quad \int_{\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}} |f(x) - \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x)|^p h(x) \, dx$$

where \mathcal{W}_d is as in (3) and where $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}$ is as in (5). Then there exists a $\mathbb{W}' \in \mathcal{W}_d$ such that $\text{err}^p(\mathbb{W}') = \inf_{\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d} \text{err}^p(\mathbb{W})$.

Loosely speaking, Theorem 1.1 reveals in the situation of *shallow residual ReLU ANNs* with a d_{in} -dimensional input layer (with d_{in} neurons on the input layer), with a d -dimensional hidden layer (with d neurons on the hidden layer), and with a skip-connection from the input layer to the output layer that there exist minimizers in the loss optimization landscape for the L^p -loss.

Theorem 1.1 is a direct consequence of the more general Theorem 1.2 below. For this, let $\mu: \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a finite measure on the Borel sets of $\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$, let $\mathbb{D} = \text{supp}(\mu)$ be the support of μ , and let $\mathcal{L}: \mathbb{D} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a product measurable function, the *loss function*. We aim to minimize the error

$$(7) \quad \text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbb{W}) = \int_{\mathbb{D}} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x)) \, d\mu(x)$$

over all $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ for a given $d \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and we let

$$(8) \quad \text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} = \inf_{\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d} \text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbb{W})$$

the minimal error with d neurons on the hidden layer. We stress that if there does not exist a neural network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ satisfying $\text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbb{W}) = \text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}}$ then every sequence $(\mathbb{W}_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{W}_d$ of networks satisfying $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbb{W}_n) = \text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}}$ diverges to infinity.

It follows the main result.

Theorem 1.2 (Existence of minimizers – general loss functions and fully-connected residual ANNs). *Assume that $\mathbb{D} = \text{supp}(\mu)$ is compact, assume that μ has a continuous Lebesgue density $h: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, assume that for every hyperplane $H \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ intersecting the interior of the convex hull of \mathbb{D} there is an element $x \in H$ with $h(x) > 0$, and assume that the loss function $\mathcal{L}: \mathbb{D} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ satisfies the following assumptions:*

- (i) *(Continuity in the first argument) For every $y \in \mathbb{R}$ it holds that $\mathbb{D} \ni x \mapsto \mathcal{L}(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}$ is continuous.*
- (ii) *(Strict convexity in the second argument) For all $x \in \mathbb{D}$ it holds that $\mathbb{R} \ni y \mapsto \mathcal{L}(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}$ is strictly convex and attains its minimum.*

Then it holds for every $d \in \mathbb{N}_0$ that there exists an optimal network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ with $\text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbb{W}) = \text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}}$.

Theorem 1.2 is an immediate consequence of Proposition 4.3 below. In the following example we apply the main theorem for regression problems. In particular, the arguments entail validity of Theorem 1.1.

Example 1.3 (Regression problem). *Let μ be as in Theorem 1.2, let $f: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous, and let $L: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a strictly convex function that attains its minimum. Then the function $\mathcal{L}: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ given by*

$$(9) \quad \mathcal{L}(x, y) = L(y - f(x))$$

for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ and $y \in \mathbb{R}$ satisfies the assumptions of Theorem 1.2 and Theorem 1.2 allows us to conclude that the infimum

$$(10) \quad \inf_{\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d} \int L(\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x) - f(x)) \, d\mu(x)$$

is attained for a network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$.

Our proof technique is different from the one in [JR22]. In [JR22], it is shown that for the approximation of a one-dimensional Lipschitz target function f on the interval $[0, 1]$ one can restrict attention to ANNs having a response whose Lipschitz constant is bounded by $d\|f\|_{\text{Lip}[0,1]}$, where d denotes the number of neurons on the hidden layer. Since the latter is a compact space one can deduce existence of global minimizers. In this work, we first propose a closure of the space of response functions consisting of all network responses and additional limiting functions that are discontinuous. In a second step, we apply convexity arguments to construct for each discontinuous function in the functions space a network response that performs strictly better in the approximation of f . Both steps work in arbitrary input dimension, for arbitrary (possible non Lipschitz continuous) target functions f and only uses the strict convexity of the loss function.

We note that the set of the realization functions of shallow residual ReLU ANNs with d_{in} neurons on the input layer, with d neurons on the hidden layer, and with a skip-connection from the input layer to the output layer coincides with the set of the realization functions of shallow fully-connected feedforward ANNs with d_{in} neurons on the input layer, with $d + 1$

neurons on the hidden layer, with the ReLU activation for d neurons on the hidden layer, and with the identity activation for the remaining neuron on the hidden layer. Moreover, the class of responses $\{\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}: \mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d\}$ that is considered in this article clearly contains all responses of shallow ANNs having only d ReLU neurons on the hidden layer and no skip connection. Conversely, since an affine function $\mathbf{a}: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ can be represented as the response of two ReLU neurons, $\{\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}: \mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d\}$ is also contained in the class of responses of shallow ANNs using $d + 2$ neurons on the hidden layer that all apply the ReLU activation function. If μ is compactly supported, then the \mathbb{D} -restricted responses in $\{\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}: \mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d\}$ even can be expressed by shallow ReLU networks with $d + 1$ neurons.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. In Section 2, we summarize properties of the loss landscape in supervised learning and convergence statements for GD methods known in the literature. We stress that the analysis of the loss landscape is of particular interest since it effects the dynamics of all applied optimization methods. In Section 3, we propose a closure of the space of response functions which contains all responses of shallow ReLU ANNs and additional discontinuous limit functions. In Section 4, we show that the newly added functions are suboptimal. Moreover, we give a counterexample for Theorem 1.1 in the case that $h^{-1}((0, \infty))$ is a non-convex set, see Example 4.4. We also give a necessary and sufficient condition that guarantees that the minimal error in the regression task strictly decreases after adding a ReLU neuron to the network architecture, see Proposition 4.5 and Example 4.7.

2. RELATED WORK

The loss landscape in supervised learning: The analysis of the loss landscape in supervised learning is of special interest since its structure is important regardless of the applied optimization algorithm. In the overparametrized regime, one can use Sard’s theorem to show that, for smooth activation functions, the set of global minima forms for almost all input data a smooth manifold [Coo21]. In [DK22b], the positive homogeneity of the ReLU activation is used to show that the configurations of shallow ReLU ANNs having the same response function is a smooth manifold, if one uses the minimal necessary number of neurons on the hidden layer in order to construct the particular response. This work also gives a sufficient condition for piecewise affine functions which implies that they can be written as responses of shallow ReLU ANNs. [Liu21] shows that, in the situation of shallow ReLU ANNs and finitely many data points, differentiable local minima are optimal within their cell of fixed activation pattern. They also give a criterion for when there exist non-differentiable local minima on the border of those cells. For the approximation of affine target functions one is able to completely classify the critical points and show the abstinence of local maxima [CJR22]. For statements about the existence of and convergence to *non-optimal local minima* in the training of (shallow) networks we refer the reader, e.g., to [SCP16, SS18, VBB19, CK23, GW22, IJR22]. See [LXT⁺18] for visualizations of the loss landscape for various choices of network architectures. A good literature review regarding the loss landscape in neural network training can be found in [EMWW20]. See also [KKV03] for a result concerning the existence of a global minimum in the regression task of approximating functions in the space $L^p([0, 1]^d)$ with shallow ANNs using *heavyside activation*. Moreover, we refer to [Sin70] for a general introduction into best approximators in normed spaces.

Convergence results for GD type optimization methods: Several statements on the convergence of GD type optimization methods under the assumption (1) have been obtained in the literature. We refer the reader to [BDL07, EJRW23, JR22] for results concerning gradient flows, to [AMA05, AB09] for results concerning deterministic gradient methods, to [Tad15, DDKL20, MHKC20, DK21] for results concerning stochastic gradient methods and to [DK22a]

for results concerning gradient based diffusion processes. Many of these results exploit *Kurdyka-Lojasiewicz* gradient type inequalities to establish convergence to a point (often a critical point) of the considered GD type optimization methods and we refer the reader to [Loj63, Loj65, Loj84] for classical results by Lojasiewicz concerning gradient inequalities for analytic target functions and direct consequences for the convergence of gradient flows. In order to achieve (1), weight regularization can also be used to keep (stochastic) gradient descent from diverging, see [DK23, Lemma D.1].

In the overparametrized setting, the stochastic noise in single-batch or mini-batch GD optimization methods vanishes when approaching the global minimum. This fact can be used to derive exponential convergence rates, see [Woj23, GK23]. For sophisticated convergence analysis for GD optimization methods in overparametrized regimes we point, e.g., to [CB18, DZPS19, DLL⁺19, CB20, Woj20] and the references therein.

3. GENERALIZED RESPONSE OF NEURAL NETWORKS

We will work with more intuitive geometric descriptions of realization functions of networks $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$. We slightly modify the ideas given in [DK22b] and later introduce the notion of a *generalized response*. Then, we show in Proposition 3.5 that, in very general approximation problems, there always exists a generalized response that solves the minimization task at least as well as the class $\{\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}} : \mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d\}$.

We call a network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ *non-degenerate* iff for all $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, d\}$ we have $w_j^1 \neq 0$. For a non-degenerate network \mathbb{W} , we say that the neuron $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, d\}$ has

- *normal* $\mathbf{n}_j = |w_j^1|^{-1} w_j^1 \in \mathbb{S}^{d_{\text{in}}-1} := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : |x| = 1\}$,
- *offset* $o_j = -|w_j^1|^{-1} b_j \in \mathbb{R}$, and
- *kink* $\Delta_j = |w_j^1| w_j^2 \in \mathbb{R}$.

Moreover, we call the affine mapping $\mathbf{a} : \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ given by

$$(11) \quad \mathbf{a}(x) = w_0^1 \cdot x + b_0$$

affine background. We call $(\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a})$ with $\mathbf{n} = (\mathbf{n}_1, \dots, \mathbf{n}_d) \in (\mathbb{S}^{d_{\text{in}}-1})^d$, $o = (o_1, \dots, o_d) \in \mathbb{R}^d$, $\Delta = (\Delta_1, \dots, \Delta_d) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and the affine function \mathbf{a} the *effective tuple* of \mathbb{W} and write \mathcal{E}_d for the set of all effective tuples using d ReLU neurons.

First, we note that the response of a non-degenerate ANN \mathbb{W} can be represented in terms of its effective tuple:

$$(12) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x) &= \mathbf{a}(x) + \sum_{j=1}^d w_j^2 (w_j^1 \cdot x + b_j)^+ = \mathbf{a}(x) + \sum_{j=1}^d \Delta_j \left(\frac{1}{|w_j^1|} w_j^1 \cdot x + \frac{1}{|w_j^1|} b_j \right)^+ \\ &= \mathbf{a}(x) + \sum_{j=1}^d \Delta_j (\mathbf{n}_j \cdot x - o_j)^+. \end{aligned}$$

With slight misuse of notation we also write

$$(13) \quad \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a}} : \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad x \mapsto \mathbf{a}(x) + \sum_{j=1}^d \Delta_j (\mathbf{n}_j \cdot x - o_j)^+$$

and $\text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a}) = \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a}}(x)) d\mu(x)$. Although the tuple $(\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a})$ does not uniquely describe a neural network, it fully characterizes the response function and thus we will speak of the neural network with effective tuple $(\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a})$.

We stress that also the response of a degenerate network \mathbb{W} can be described as response associated to an effective tuple. Indeed, for every $j \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ with $w_j^1 = 0$ the respective neuron has a constant contribution $w_j^2(b_j)^+$. Now, one can choose an arbitrary normal \mathbf{n}_j and offset o_j , set the kink equal to zero ($\Delta_j = 0$) and add the constant $w_j^2(b_j)^+$ to the affine background \mathbf{a} . Repeating this procedure for every such neuron we get an effective tuple $(\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{E}_d$ that satisfies $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a}} = \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}$. Conversely, for every effective tuple $(\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{E}_d$, the mapping $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a}}$ is the response of an appropriate network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$. In fact, for $j = 1, \dots, d$, one can choose $w_j^1 = \mathbf{n}_j$, $b_j = -o_j$ and $w_j^2 = \Delta_j$ and gets that for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$

$$(14) \quad w_j^2(w_j^1 \cdot x + b_j)^+ = \Delta_j(\mathbf{n}_j \cdot x - o_j)^+.$$

Analogously, one can choose $w_0^1 = \mathbf{a}'$ and $b_0 = \mathbf{a}(0)$ such that for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$

$$(15) \quad \mathbf{a}(x) = w_0^1 \cdot x + b_0.$$

This entails that

$$(16) \quad \text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} = \inf_{(\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathcal{E}_d} \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{b}}(x)) \, d\mu(x)$$

and the infimum is attained iff there is a network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ for which the infimum in (8) is attained.

For an effective tuple $(\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a}) \in \mathcal{E}_d$, we say that the j th ReLU neuron has the *breakline*

$$(17) \quad H_j = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \mathbf{n}_j \cdot x = o_j\}$$

and we call

$$(18) \quad A_j = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \mathbf{n}_j \cdot x > o_j\}$$

the *domain of activity* of the j th ReLU neuron. By construction, we have

$$(19) \quad \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a}}(x) = \mathbf{a}(x) + \sum_{j=1}^d (\Delta_j(\mathbf{n}_j \cdot x - o_j)) \mathbb{1}_{A_j}(x).$$

Outside the breaklines the function $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a}}$ is differentiable with

$$(20) \quad D\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbf{n}, o, \Delta, \mathbf{a}}(x) = \mathbf{a}'(x) + \sum_{j=1}^d \Delta_j \mathbf{n}_j \mathbb{1}_{A_j}(x).$$

Note that for each summand $j = 1, \dots, d$ along the breakline the difference of the differential on A_j and $\overline{A_j}^c$ equals $\Delta_j \mathbf{n}_j$ (which is also true for the response function $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}$ provided that it is differentiable in the reference points and there does not exist a second neuron having the same breakline H_j).

For a better understanding of the optimization problem discussed in this article it makes sense to view the set of responses $\{\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}} : \mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d\}$ as a subset of the locally convex vector space $\mathcal{L}_{\text{loc}}^1$ of locally integrable functions. Then the set of response functions is not closed in $\mathcal{L}_{\text{loc}}^1$ and the main task of this article is to show that functions in $\mathcal{L}_{\text{loc}}^1$ that can be approached by functions from $\{\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}} : \mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d\}$ but are itself no response functions will provide larger errors than the response functions.

We now extend the family of response functions.

Definition 3.1. We call a function $\mathcal{R} : \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a generalized response if it admits the following representation: there are $K \in \mathbb{N}_0$, a tuple of open half-spaces $\mathbf{A} = (A_1, \dots, A_K)$ of $\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ with

pairwise distinct boundaries $\partial A_1, \dots, \partial A_K$, a vector $\mathbf{m} = (m_1, \dots, m_K) \in \{1, 2\}^K$, an affine mapping $\mathbf{a}: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, vectors $\delta_1, \dots, \delta_K \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$, and reals $\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_K \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

(i) it holds for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ that

$$(21) \quad \mathcal{R}(x) = \mathbf{a}(x) + \sum_{k=1}^K (\delta_k \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_k) \mathbb{1}_{A_k}(x)$$

and

(ii) it holds for all $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ with $m_k = 1$ that

$$(22) \quad \partial A_k \subseteq \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}: \delta_k \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_k = 0\}.$$

We will represent generalized responses as in (21), we call A_1, \dots, A_K the active half-spaces of the response, and we call m_1, \dots, m_K the multiplicities of the half-spaces A_1, \dots, A_K . The minimal number $m_1 + \dots + m_K$ that can be achieved in such a representation is called the dimension of \mathcal{R} . For every $d \in \mathbb{N}_0$ we denote by \mathfrak{R}_d the family of all generalized responses of dimension d or smaller. We call a generalized response simple if it is continuous which means that all multiplicities can be chosen equal to one. A response $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{R}_d$ is called strict at dimension d if the response has dimension $d - 1$ or is discontinuous. We denote by $\mathfrak{R}_d^{\text{strict}}$ the responses in \mathfrak{R}_d that are strict at dimension d .

Remark 3.2. Note that the sets $\{\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}: \mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d\}$ and $\{\mathcal{R}: \mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{R}_d \text{ is simple}\}$ agree.

The condition $\partial A_k \subseteq \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}: \delta_k \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_k = 0\}$ is equivalent to the condition that $x \mapsto (\delta_k \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_k) \mathbb{1}_{A_k}(x)$ is continuous which, in particular, implies that $\delta_k \perp \partial A_k$. The next remark shows that every generalized response $\mathcal{R}: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of dimension d or smaller (even the generalized responses with $\delta_k \not\perp \partial A_k$ for some k) is, on $\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \setminus (\bigcup_{k=1, \dots, K} \partial A_k)$, the limit of network responses of networks in \mathcal{W}_d .

Remark 3.3 (Asymptotic ANN representations for generalized responses). Let $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{S}^{d_{\text{in}}-1}$, $\delta \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ and $o, \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}$ and set

$$(23) \quad A = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}: \mathbf{n} \cdot x > o\} \quad \text{and} \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}: \mathcal{R}(x) = (\delta \cdot x + \mathbf{b}) \mathbb{1}_A(x).$$

We will show that the generalized response \mathcal{R} is on $\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \setminus (\partial A)$ the limit of the response of two ReLU neurons. For every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the following function

$$(24) \quad \mathcal{R}_n(x) = \frac{1}{2}((\delta + n\mathbf{n}) \cdot x + \mathbf{b} - no)^+ - \frac{1}{2}((-\delta + n\mathbf{n}) \cdot x - \mathbf{b} - no)^+$$

is the response of a shallow ReLU ANN with two hidden ReLU neurons. Now note that for all $x \in A$ one has $\mathbf{n} \cdot x - o > 0$ so that

$$(25) \quad (\delta + n\mathbf{n}) \cdot x + \mathbf{b} - no = n(\mathbf{n} \cdot x - o) + \delta \cdot x + \mathbf{b} \rightarrow \infty.$$

Analogously, $(-\delta + n\mathbf{n}) \cdot x - \mathbf{b} - no \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, there exists an $N \in \mathbb{N}$ depending on x such that for all $n \geq N$

$$(26) \quad \mathcal{R}_n(x) = \delta \cdot x + \mathbf{b} = \mathcal{R}(x).$$

Conversely, for all $x \in \overline{A}^c$ one has $\mathbf{n} \cdot x - o < 0$ so that analogously to above $(\delta + n\mathbf{n}) \cdot x + \mathbf{b} - no \rightarrow -\infty$ and $(-\delta + n\mathbf{n}) \cdot x - \mathbf{b} - no \rightarrow -\infty$. Consequently, there exists an $N \in \mathbb{N}$ depending on x such that for all $n \geq N$

$$(27) \quad \mathcal{R}_n(x) = 0 = \mathcal{R}(x).$$

We thus represented \mathcal{R} as asymptotic response of a ReLU ANN with two hidden neurons.

For a generalized response one replaces every term $(\delta_k \cdot x + \mathfrak{b})\mathbb{1}_{A_k}(x)$ of multiplicity two (see (21)) by two ReLU neurons exactly as above. Moreover, the terms with multiplicity one are responses of ANNs with one ReLU neuron.

In this section, we work with a general measure μ which may have unbounded support. The assumptions on μ are stated in the next definition.

Definition 3.4. (i) An element x of a hyperplane $H \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ is called H -regular if $x \in \text{supp } \mu|_A$ and $x \in \text{supp } \mu|_{\overline{A}^c}$, where A is an open half-space with $\partial A = H$.
(ii) A measure μ is called nice if all hyperplanes have μ -measure zero and if for every open half-space A with $\mu(A), \mu(\overline{A}^c) > 0$ the set of ∂A -regular points cannot be covered by finitely many hyperplanes different from ∂A .

Next, we will show that under quite weak assumptions there exist generalized responses of dimension d or smaller that achieve an error of at most $\text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}}$.

Proposition 3.5. Assume that μ is a nice measure on a closed subset $\mathbb{D} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ of $\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ and assume that the loss function $\mathcal{L}: \mathbb{D} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is measurable and satisfies the following assumptions:

(i) (Lower-semicontinuity in the second argument) For all $x \in \mathbb{D}$, $y \in \mathbb{R}$ we have

$$(28) \quad \liminf_{y' \rightarrow y} \mathcal{L}(x, y') \geq \mathcal{L}(x, y).$$

(ii) (Unbounded in the second argument) For all $x \in \mathbb{D}$ we have

$$(29) \quad \lim_{|y| \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{L}(x, y) = \infty.$$

Let $d \in \mathbb{N}_0$ with $\text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} < \infty$. Then there exists a generalized response $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{R}_d$ which satisfies

$$(30) \quad \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x)) d\mu(x) = \overline{\text{err}}_d^{\mathcal{L}} := \inf_{\tilde{\mathcal{R}} \in \mathfrak{R}_d} \int \mathcal{L}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x)) d\mu(x).$$

Furthermore, if $d \geq 1$, then the infimum

$$(31) \quad \inf_{\tilde{\mathcal{R}} \in \mathfrak{R}_d^{\text{strict}}} \int \mathcal{L}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x)) d\mu(x)$$

is attained on $\mathfrak{R}_d^{\text{strict}}$.

Proof. Let $(\mathcal{R}^{(n)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence of generalized responses in \mathfrak{R}_d that satisfies

$$(32) \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}^{(n)}(x)) d\mu(x) = \overline{\text{err}}_d^{\mathcal{L}}.$$

We use the representations as in (21) and write

$$(33) \quad \mathcal{R}^{(n)}(x) = \mathfrak{a}^{(n)}(x) + \sum_{k=1}^{K_n} (\delta_k^{(n)} \cdot x + \mathfrak{b}_k^{(n)}) \mathbb{1}_{A_k^{(n)}}(x).$$

Moreover, denote by $\mathbf{n}_k^{(n)} \in \mathbb{S}^{d_{\text{in}}-1}$ and $o_k^{(n)} \in \mathbb{R}$ the quantities with $A_k^{(n)} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \mathbf{n}_k^{(n)} \cdot x > o_k^{(n)}\}$ and by $\mathbf{m}^{(n)} = (m_1^{(n)}, \dots, m_{K^{(n)}}^{(n)})$ the respective multiplicities.

1. Step: Choosing an appropriate subsequence.

Since $K^{(n)} \leq d$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we can choose a subsequence $(\ell_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ such that there exists $K \in \mathbb{N}_0$ with $K^{(\ell_n)} = K$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. For ease of notation we will assume that this is the case for the full sequence. With the same argument we can assume without loss of generality that there exists $\mathbf{m} = (m_1, \dots, m_K) \in \{1, 2\}^K$ such that for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we have $\mathbf{m}^{(n)} = \mathbf{m}$.

Moreover, after possibly thinning the sequence again we can assure that for all $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ we have convergence $\mathbf{n}_k^{(n)} \rightarrow \mathbf{n}_k$ in the compact space $\mathbb{S}^{d_{\text{in}}-1}$ and $o_k^{(n)} \rightarrow o_k$ in the two point compactification $\mathbb{R} \cup \{\pm\infty\}$. We assign each $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ an *asymptotic active area* A_k given by

$$(34) \quad A_k = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \mathbf{n}_k \cdot x > o_k\}$$

which is degenerate in the case where $o_k \in \{\pm\infty\}$.

We denote by H_k the respective breakline ∂A_k . Even if, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the original breaklines $\partial A_1^{(n)}, \dots, \partial A_K^{(n)}$ are pairwise distinct, this might not be true for the limiting ones. In particular, there may be several k 's for which the asymptotic active areas may be on opposite sides of the same breakline. In that case we choose one side and replace for each k with asymptotic active area on the opposite side its contribution in the representation (21) from $(\delta_k^{(n)} \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_k^{(n)}) \mathbb{1}_{A_k^{(n)}}(x)$ to

$$(35) \quad (-\delta_k^{(n)} \cdot x - \mathbf{b}_k^{(n)}) \mathbb{1}_{(\overline{A_k^{(n)}})^c}(x) + \delta_k^{(n)} \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_k^{(n)}$$

which agrees with the former term outside the breakline (which is a zero set). This means we replace $\delta_k^{(n)}$, $\mathbf{b}_k^{(n)}$, and $A_k^{(n)}$ by $-\delta_k^{(n)}$, $-\mathbf{b}_k^{(n)}$, and $(\overline{A_k^{(n)}})^c$, respectively, and adjust the respective affine background accordingly. Thus we can assume without loss of generality that all asymptotic active areas sharing the same breakline are on the same side.

We use the asymptotic active areas to partition the space: let \mathbb{J} denote the collection of all subsets $J \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ for which the set

$$(36) \quad A_J = \left(\bigcap_{j \in J} A_j\right) \cap \left(\bigcap_{j \in J^c} \overline{A_j}^c\right)$$

satisfies $\mu(A_J) > 0$. We note that the sets A_J , $J \in \mathbb{J}$, are non-empty, open, and pairwise disjoint and their union has full μ -measure since

$$(37) \quad \mu\left(\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \setminus \bigcup_{J \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, K\}} A_J\right) \leq \sum_{j=1}^K \mu(H_j) = 0.$$

Moreover, for every $J \in \mathbb{J}$ and every compact set B with $B \subseteq A_J$ one has from a B -dependent n onward that the generalized response $\mathcal{R}^{(n)}$ satisfies for all $x \in B$ that

$$(38) \quad \mathcal{R}^{(n)}(x) = \mathcal{D}_J^{(n)} \cdot x + \beta_J^{(n)},$$

where

$$(39) \quad \mathcal{D}_J^{(n)} := \mathbf{a}'^{(n)} + \sum_{j \in J} \delta_j^{(n)} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_J^{(n)} := \mathbf{a}^{(n)}(0) + \sum_{j \in J} \mathbf{b}_j^{(n)}.$$

Let $J \in \mathbb{J}$. Next, we show that along an appropriate subsequence, we have convergence of $(\mathcal{D}_J^{(n)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$. First assume that along a subsequence one has that $(|\mathcal{D}_J^{(n)}|)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges to ∞ . For ease of notation we assume without loss of generality that $|\mathcal{D}_J^{(n)}| \rightarrow \infty$. We let

$$(40) \quad \mathcal{H}_J^{(n)} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \mathcal{D}_J^{(n)} \cdot x + \beta_J^{(n)} = 0\}.$$

For every n with $\mathcal{D}_J^{(n)} \neq 0$, $\mathcal{H}_J^{(n)}$ is a hyperplane which can be parametrized by taking a normal and the respective offset. As above we can argue that along an appropriate subsequence (which is again assumed to be the whole sequence) one has convergence of the normals in $\mathbb{S}^{d_{\text{in}}-1}$ and of the offsets in $\mathbb{R} \cup \{\pm\infty\}$. We denote by \mathcal{H}_J the hyperplane being associated to the limiting normal and offset (which is assumed to be the empty set in the case where the offsets do not converge

in \mathbb{R}). Since the norm of the gradient $\mathcal{D}_J^{(n)}$ tends to infinity we get that for every $x \in A_J \setminus \mathcal{H}_J$ one has $|\mathcal{R}^{(n)}(x)| \rightarrow \infty$ and, hence, $\mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}^{(n)}(x)) \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, Fatou implies that

$$(41) \quad \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{A_J \setminus \mathcal{H}_J} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}^{(n)}(x)) \, d\mu(x) \geq \int_{A_J \setminus \mathcal{H}_J} \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}^{(n)}(x)) \, d\mu(x) = \infty$$

contradicting the asymptotic optimality of $(\mathcal{R}^{(n)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. We showed that the sequence $(\mathcal{D}_J^{(n)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is precompact and by switching to an appropriate subsequence we can guarantee that the limit $\mathcal{D}_J = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{D}_J^{(n)}$ exists.

Similarly we show that along an appropriate subsequence $(\beta_J^{(n)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges to a value $\beta_J \in \mathbb{R}$. Suppose this were not the case, then there were a subsequence along which $|\beta_J^{(n)}| \rightarrow \infty$ (again we assume for ease of notation that this is the case along the full sequence). Then for every $x \in A_J$, $|\mathcal{R}^{(n)}(x)| \rightarrow \infty$ and we argue as above that this contradicts the optimality of $(\mathcal{R}^{(n)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. Consequently, we have for an appropriately thinned sequence on a compact set $B \subseteq A_J$ uniform convergence

$$(42) \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{R}^{(n)}(x) = \mathcal{D}_J \cdot x + \beta_J.$$

Since $\bigcup_{J \in \mathbb{J}} A_J$ has full μ -measure we get with the lower semicontinuity of \mathcal{L} in the second argument and Fatou's lemma that for every measurable function $\mathcal{R}: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfying for each $J \in \mathbb{J}$, $x \in A_J$ that

$$(43) \quad \mathcal{R}(x) = \mathcal{D}_J \cdot x + \beta_J$$

we have

$$(44) \quad \begin{aligned} \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x)) \, d\mu(x) &= \int \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}^{(n)}(x)) \, d\mu(x) \\ &\leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}^{(n)}(x)) \, d\mu(x) = \overline{\text{err}}_d^{\mathcal{L}}. \end{aligned}$$

Step 2: \mathcal{R} may be chosen as a generalized response of dimension d or smaller.

We call a summand $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ degenerate if A_k or \overline{A}_k^c has μ -measure zero. We omit every degenerate summand k in the sense that we set $\delta_k^{(n)} = 0$ and $\mathfrak{b}_k^{(n)} = 0$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and note that by adjusting the affine background appropriately we still have validity of (42) with the same limit on all relevant cells and, in particular, μ -almost everywhere.

Let now k be a non-degenerate summand. Since μ is nice there exists a ∂A_k -regular point x that is not in $\bigcup_{A \in \mathbb{A}: A \neq A_k} \partial A$, where $\mathbb{A} := \{A_j: j \text{ is non-degenerate}\}$. We let

$$(45) \quad J_-^x = \{j: x \in A_j\} \quad \text{and} \quad J_+^x = J_-^x \cup \{j: A_j = A_k\}.$$

Since $x \in \text{supp}(\mu|_{\overline{A}_j^c})$ we get that the cell $A_{J_-^x}$ has strictly positive μ -measure so that $J_-^x \in \mathbb{J}$. Analogously, $x \in \text{supp}(\mu|_{A_j})$ entails that $J_+^x \in \mathbb{J}$. (Note that J_+^x and J_-^x are just the cells that lie on the opposite sides of the hyperplane ∂A_k at x .) We thus get that

$$(46) \quad \delta_{A_k}^{(n)} := \sum_{j: A_j = A_k} \delta_j^{(n)} = \mathcal{D}_{J_+^x}^{(n)} - \mathcal{D}_{J_-^x}^{(n)} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_{J_+^x} - \mathcal{D}_{J_-^x} =: \delta_{A_k},$$

where the definitions of $\delta_{A_k}^{(n)}$ and δ_{A_k} do not depend on the choice of x . Analogously,

$$(47) \quad \mathfrak{b}_{A_k}^{(n)} := \sum_{j: A_j = A_k} \mathfrak{b}_j^{(n)} = \beta_{J_+^x}^{(n)} - \beta_{J_-^x}^{(n)} \rightarrow \beta_{J_+^x} - \beta_{J_-^x} =: \mathfrak{b}_{A_k}.$$

Now for general $J \in \mathbb{J}$, we have

$$(48) \quad \mathcal{D}_J \leftarrow \mathcal{D}_J^{(n)} = \mathbf{a}'^{(n)} + \sum_{A \in \{A_j: j \in J\}} \delta_A^{(n)} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_J \leftarrow \beta_J^{(n)} = \mathbf{a}^{(n)}(0) + \sum_{A \in \{A_j: j \in J\}} \mathbf{b}_A^{(n)}.$$

Since $\sum_{A \in \{A_j: j \in J\}} \delta_A^{(n)}$ and $\sum_{A \in \{A_j: j \in J\}} \mathbf{b}_A^{(n)}$ converge to $\sum_{A \in \{A_j: j \in J\}} \delta_A$ and $\sum_{A \in \{A_j: j \in J\}} \mathbf{b}_A$, respectively, we have that $(\mathbf{a}'^{(n)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ and $(\mathbf{a}^{(n)}(0))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converge and there is an appropriate affine function \mathbf{a} such that for all $J \in \mathbb{J}$ and $x \in A_J$

$$(49) \quad \mathcal{R}(x) = \mathcal{D}_J \cdot x + \beta_J = \mathbf{a}(x) + \sum_{A \in \mathbb{A}} (\delta_A \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_A) \mathbb{1}_A(x).$$

So far, we have only used the definition of \mathcal{R} on $\bigcup_{J \in \mathbb{J}} A_J$ and we now assume that \mathcal{R} is chosen in such a way that the latter identity holds for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ (by possibly changing the definition on a μ -nullset). We still need to show that \mathcal{R} is a generalized response of dimension d or smaller.

Every active area $A \in \mathbb{A}$ that is the asymptotic active area of a single non-degenerate summand k with $m_k = 1$ is assigned the multiplicity one. All other non-degenerate active areas get multiplicity two. Then the overall multiplicity (the sum of the individual multiplicities) is smaller or equal to the dimension d . To see this recall that every active area $A \in \mathbb{A}$ that is the asymptotic area of more than one summand or one summand of multiplicity two also contributed at least two to the multiplicity of the approximating responses. All degenerate summands do not contribute at all although they contribute to the approximating responses.

It remains to show that \mathcal{R} is indeed a generalized response with the active areas \mathbb{A} having the above multiplicities. For this it remains to show continuity of $\mathbb{1}_A(x)(\delta_A \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_A)$ for all $A \in \mathbb{A}$ with assigned multiplicity one. Suppose that the k th summand is the unique summand that contributes to such an A . Then $\delta_k^{(n)} = \delta_A^{(n)} \rightarrow \delta_A$ and $\mathbf{b}_k^{(n)} = \mathbf{b}_A^{(n)} \rightarrow \mathbf{b}_A$. Moreover, one has

$$(50) \quad \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \mathbf{n}_k^{(n)} \cdot x - o_k^{(n)} = 0\} \subseteq \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \delta_k^{(n)} \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_k^{(n)} = 0\}$$

which entails that, in particular, $\delta_k^{(n)}$ is a multiple of $\mathbf{n}_k^{(n)}$. Both latter vectors converge which also entails that the limit δ_A is a multiple of \mathbf{n}_k . To show that

$$(51) \quad \partial A \subseteq \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \delta_A \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_A = 0\}$$

is satisfied it thus suffices to verify that one point of the set on the left-hand side lies also in the set on the right-hand side. This is indeed the case since $o_k \mathbf{n}_k$ is in the set on the left-hand side and

$$(52) \quad \delta_A \cdot (o_k \mathbf{n}_k) + \mathbf{b}_A = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \underbrace{\delta_k^{(n)} \cdot (o_k^{(n)} \mathbf{n}_k^{(n)})}_{=0} + \mathbf{b}_k^{(n)},$$

where we used that $x = o_k^{(n)} \mathbf{n}_k^{(n)}$ satisfies by assumption $\delta_k^{(n)} \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_k^{(n)} = 0$.

Step 3: The infimum over all strict responses is attained.

We suppose that $(\mathcal{R}^{(n)})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a sequence of strict generalized responses satisfying

$$(53) \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}^{(n)}(x)) d\mu(x) = \inf_{\tilde{\mathcal{R}} \in \mathfrak{R}_d^{\text{strict}}} \int \mathcal{L}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x)) d\mu(x).$$

Then we can find a subsequence of responses in \mathfrak{R}_{d-1} or a subsequence of responses where at least one active area has multiplicity two. In the former case the response constructed above is a generalized response of dimension $d-1$ or lower which is strict at dimension d . Conversely, in the latter case the construction from above will lead to a generalized response that has at

least one active area with multiplicity two which, in turn, implies that \mathcal{R} is either of dimension strictly smaller than d or is discontinuous. \square

4. DISCONTINUOUS RESPONSES ARE NOT OPTIMAL

In this section, we show that generalized responses that contain discontinuities are not optimal in the minimization task for a loss function that is continuous in the first argument and strict convex in the second argument. This proves Theorem 1.2 since all continuous generalized responses can be represented by shallow residual ReLU networks.

In the proofs we will make use of the following properties of the loss functions \mathcal{L} under consideration.

Lemma 4.1. *Let $\mathcal{L}: \mathbb{D} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a function satisfying the following assumptions:*

- (i) *(Continuity in the first argument) For every $y \in \mathbb{R}$ it holds that $\mathbb{D} \ni x \mapsto \mathcal{L}(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}$ is continuous.*
- (ii) *(Strict convexity in the second argument) For all $x \in \mathbb{D}$ it holds that $\mathbb{R} \ni y \mapsto \mathcal{L}(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}$ is strictly convex and attains its minimum.*

Then

- (I) *it holds that $\mathcal{L}: \mathbb{D} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is continuous,*
- (II) *it holds for every compact $K \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ that the function $\mathbb{D} \ni x \mapsto \mathcal{L}(x, \cdot)|_K \in C(K, \mathbb{R})$ is continuous with respect to the supremum norm,*
- (III) *it holds that there exists a unique $\mathbf{m}: \mathbb{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ which satisfies for every $x \in \mathbb{D}$ that*

$$(54) \quad \mathcal{L}(x, \mathbf{m}(x)) = \min_{y \in \mathbb{R}} \mathcal{L}(x, y),$$

and

- (IV) *it holds that $\mathbf{m}: \mathbb{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathbb{D} \ni x \mapsto \min_{y \in \mathbb{R}} \mathcal{L}(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}$ are continuous.*

Proof. Regarding (I): The proof can, e.g., be found in [Roc70, Theorem 10.7].

Regarding (II): The proof can, e.g., be found in [Roc70, Theorem 10.8].

Regarding (III): The existence and uniqueness of $\mathbf{m}: \mathbb{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an immediate consequence of property (ii).

Regarding (IV): We show continuity of $x \mapsto \min_y \mathcal{L}(x, y)$ and $x \mapsto \mathbf{m}(x)$. Let $x' \in \mathbb{D}$ and choose $y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ with $y_1 < \mathbf{m}(x') < y_2$. Now, there exists a neighborhood $U \subseteq \mathbb{D}$ of x' such that

$$(55) \quad \mathcal{L}(x, \mathbf{m}(x')) < \mathcal{L}(x, y_1) \wedge \mathcal{L}(x, y_2)$$

for all $x \in U$ and with the strict convexity of $y \mapsto \mathcal{L}(x, y)$ we get for all $y \notin [y_1, y_2]$

$$(56) \quad \mathcal{L}(x, y) \geq \mathcal{L}(x, y_1) \wedge \mathcal{L}(x, y_2).$$

Hence, for all $x \in U$ we have $\min_{y \in \mathbb{R}} \mathcal{L}(x, y) = \min_{y \in [y_1, y_2]} \mathcal{L}(x, y)$ and the continuity of $x \mapsto \min_y \mathcal{L}(x, y)$ follows from (II). Moreover, since y_1 and y_2 were arbitrary we also have continuity of $x \mapsto \mathbf{m}(x)$. \square

Clearly, we have that

$$(57) \quad \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathbf{m}(x)) \, d\mu(x) = \inf_{f \in C(\mathbb{D}, \mathbb{R})} \int \mathcal{L}(x, f(x)) \, d\mu(x)$$

so that the minimization task reduces to finding a good approximation for \mathbf{m} on the support of μ . If \mathbf{m} is the response of an ANN $\mathbb{W}' \in \mathcal{W}_d$ for $d \in \mathbb{N}$, then \mathbb{W}' minimizes the error $\mathcal{W}_d \ni \mathbb{W} \mapsto \text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbb{W}) \in \mathbb{R}$. If \mathbf{m} is not representable by a network using d ReLU neurons then one expects the minimal error to strictly decrease after adding a ReLU neuron to the network

structure, i.e., $\text{err}_{d+1}^{\mathcal{L}} < \text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}}$. This is true in many situations (see Proposition 4.5) but there exist counterexamples to this intuition (see Example 4.7).

We note that the set of generalized responses is invariant under right applications of affine transformations that are one-to-one.

Lemma 4.2. *Let $d \in \mathbb{N}_0$, let $\mathcal{R}: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a mapping, and let $\varphi: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ be an affine mapping that is injective. Then the following properties hold for \mathcal{R} iff the corresponding properties hold for $\mathcal{R} \circ \varphi$:*

- (i) $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{R}_d$
- (ii) $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{R}_d^{\text{strict}}$
- (iii) \mathcal{R} is simple.

Proof. Suppose that $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{R}_d$ is represented as in (21) with the active areas being for all $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$

$$(58) \quad A_k = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \mathbf{n}_k \cdot x > o_k\}.$$

We represent the affine function φ as $\varphi(x) = \mathcal{A}x + b$ with $\mathcal{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}} \times d_{\text{in}}}$ and $b \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$. Then obviously

$$(59) \quad \mathcal{R}(\varphi(x)) = (a \circ \varphi)(x) + \sum_{k=1}^K (\delta_k \cdot \varphi(x) + \mathbf{b}_k) \mathbb{1}_{A_k}(\varphi(x)) = \tilde{a}(x) + \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbb{1}_{\tilde{A}_k}(x) (\tilde{\delta}_k \cdot x + \tilde{\mathbf{b}}_k),$$

with $\tilde{a} = a \circ \varphi$, $\tilde{\delta}_k = \mathcal{A}^\dagger \delta_k$, $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}_k = \mathbf{b}_k + \delta_k \cdot b$, and

$$(60) \quad \tilde{A}_k = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \mathbf{n}_k \cdot (\mathcal{A}x + b) > o_k\} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : (\mathcal{A}^\dagger \mathbf{n}_k) \cdot x > o_k - \mathbf{n}_k \cdot b\}$$

where $(\cdot)^\dagger$ denotes the transpose of a vector or a matrix. Clearly, continuity of the summands is preserved and, hence, one can choose the same multiplicities. Therefore, $\mathcal{R} \circ \varphi$ is again in \mathfrak{R}_d and it is even strict at dimension d or simple if this is the case for \mathcal{R} . Applying the inverse affine transform φ^{-1} we also obtain equivalence of the properties. \square

We are now in the position to prove the main statement of this article, Theorem 1.2. It is an immediate consequence of the following result. We stress that the statement of Proposition 4.3 is stronger in the sense that it even shows that in many situations the strict generalized responses perform strictly worse than the simple responses.

Proposition 4.3. *Suppose that the assumptions of Theorem 1.2 are satisfied. Let $d \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Then there exists an optimal network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ with*

$$(61) \quad \text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbb{W}) = \text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} = \overline{\text{err}}_d^{\mathcal{L}}.$$

If additionally $d > 1$ and $\text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} < \text{err}_{d-1}^{\mathcal{L}}$, then one has that

$$(62) \quad \inf_{\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{R}_d^{\text{strict}}} \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x)) d\mu(x) > \text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}}.$$

Proof. We can assume without loss of generality that $\mu \neq 0$. First we verify the assumptions of Proposition 3.5 in order to conclude that there are generalized responses \mathcal{R} of dimension d for which

$$(63) \quad \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x)) d\mu(x) = \overline{\text{err}}_d^{\mathcal{L}}.$$

We verify that μ is a nice measure: In fact, since μ has Lebesgue-density h , we have $\mu(H) = 0$ for all hyperplanes $H \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$. Moreover, for every half-space A with $\mu(A), \mu(\bar{A}^c) > 0$ we have

that ∂A intersects the interior of the convex hull of \mathbb{D} so that there exists a point $x \in \partial A$ with $h(x) > 0$. Since $\{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : h(x) > 0\}$ is an open set, $\{x \in \partial A : h(x) > 0\}$ cannot be covered by finitely many hyperplanes different from ∂A . Moreover, since for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ the function $y \mapsto \mathcal{L}(x, y)$ is strictly convex and attains its minimum we clearly have for fixed $x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ continuity of $y \mapsto \mathcal{L}(x, y)$ and

$$(64) \quad \lim_{|y| \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{L}(x, y) = \infty.$$

We prove the remaining statements via induction over the dimension d . If $d \leq 1$, all generalized responses of dimension d are representable by a neural network and we are done. Now let $d \geq 2$ and suppose that \mathcal{R} is the best *strict* generalized response at dimension d . It suffices to show that one of the following two cases enters: one has

$$(65) \quad \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x)) \, d\mu(x) \geq \overline{\text{err}}_{d-1}^{\mathcal{L}}$$

or

$$(66) \quad \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x)) \, d\mu(x) > \overline{\text{err}}_d^{\mathcal{L}}.$$

Indeed, then in the case that (66) does not hold we have as consequence of (65)

$$(67) \quad \overline{\text{err}}_{d-1}^{\mathcal{L}} \leq \int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x)) \, d\mu(x) = \overline{\text{err}}_d^{\mathcal{L}}$$

and the induction hypothesis entails that $\text{err}_{d-1}^{\mathcal{L}} = \overline{\text{err}}_{d-1}^{\mathcal{L}} \leq \overline{\text{err}}_d^{\mathcal{L}} \leq \text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} \leq \text{err}_{d-1}^{\mathcal{L}}$ so that $\text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} = \overline{\text{err}}_d^{\mathcal{L}}$ and $\text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} = \text{err}_{d-1}^{\mathcal{L}}$. Thus, an optimal simple response \mathcal{R} of dimension $d-1$ (which exists by induction hypothesis) is also optimal when taking the minimum over all generalized responses of dimension d or smaller. Conversely, if (66) holds, an optimal generalized response (which exists by Proposition 3.5) is simple so that, in particular, $\text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} = \overline{\text{err}}_d^{\mathcal{L}}$. This shows that there always exists an optimal simple response. Moreover, it also follows that in the case where $\text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} < \text{err}_{d-1}^{\mathcal{L}}$, either of the properties (65) and (66) entail property (62).

Suppose that \mathcal{R} is given by

$$(68) \quad \mathcal{R}(x) = \mathbf{a}(x) + \sum_{k=1}^K (\delta_k \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_k) \mathbb{1}_{A_k}(x),$$

with A_1, \dots, A_K being the pairwise different activation areas and m_1, \dots, m_K being the respective multiplicities. Note that \mathcal{R} has to be discontinuous, because otherwise \mathcal{R} is of dimension strictly smaller than d and (65) holds. Therefore, we can assume without loss of generality that $m_K = 2$ and

$$(69) \quad \partial A_K \not\subseteq \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \delta_K \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_K = 0\}$$

(otherwise we reorder the terms appropriately).

If ∂A_K does not intersect the interior of \mathbb{D} , then one can replace the term $\mathbb{1}_{A_K}(x)(\delta_K \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_K)$ by $\delta_K \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_K$ or 0 without changing the error on \mathbb{D} . By doing so the new response has dimension $d-2$ or smaller. Thus, we get that

$$(70) \quad \int_{\mathbb{D}} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x)) \, d\mu(x) \geq \overline{\text{err}}_{d-2}^{\mathcal{L}}.$$

Now suppose that ∂A_K intersects the interior of \mathbb{D} . We prove that \mathcal{R} is not an optimal response in \mathfrak{R}_d by constructing a better response. To see this we apply an appropriate affine

transformation on the coordinate mapping. For an invertible matrix $B \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}} \times d_{\text{in}}}$ and a vector $c \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ we consider the invertible affine mapping

$$(71) \quad \varphi(x) = B(x + c).$$

By Lemma 4.2 the (strict) generalized responses are invariant under right applications of bijective affine transformations so that $\hat{\mathcal{R}} = \mathcal{R} \circ \varphi$ is an optimal strict generalized response for the loss function $\hat{\mathcal{L}}$ given by $\hat{\mathcal{L}}(x, y) = \mathcal{L}(x, \varphi^{-1}(y))$.

Now we distinguish two cases. In line with the notation from before we denote by $\mathbf{n}_K \in \mathbb{S}^{d_{\text{in}}-1}$ and $o_K \in \mathbb{R}$ the unique values for which $A_K = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \mathbf{n}_K \cdot x > o_K\}$. First suppose that δ_K and \mathbf{n}_K are linearly independent. We choose a basis $\tau_1, \dots, \tau_{d_{\text{in}}}$ of $\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ such that $\tau_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_K = 1$, $\tau_1 \perp \delta_K$, and for $\forall l \in (\mathbb{N} \cap [1, d_{\text{in}}]) \setminus \{1\}$: $\tau_l \perp \mathbf{n}_K$. This can be achieved by first choosing an arbitrary basis $\tau_2, \dots, \tau_{d_{\text{in}}}$ of the space of vectors being orthogonal to \mathbf{n}_K , secondly choosing a vector τ'_1 that is orthogonal to δ_K but not to \mathbf{n}_K which is possible since δ_K and \mathbf{n}_K are linearly independent and finally letting $\tau_1 = \tau'_1 / (\tau'_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_K)$.

We denote by B the matrix $(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_{d_{\text{in}}})$ consisting of the basis vectors and choose $c \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ so that

$$(72) \quad (B^\dagger \mathbf{n}_K) \cdot c = o_K \quad \text{and} \quad (B^\dagger \delta_K) \cdot c = -\mathbf{b}_K.$$

The latter is feasible since the expression on the left hand side only depends on the choice of c_1 and the expression on the right hand side only on the coordinates $c_2, \dots, c_{d_{\text{in}}}$.

As is straight-forward to verify the respective response $\hat{\mathcal{R}}$ has as K th active area $\hat{A}_K = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : x_1 > 0\}$ and on \hat{A}_K the K th summand in the respective representation of $\hat{\mathcal{R}}$ is

$$(73) \quad \delta_K \cdot \varphi(x) + \mathbf{b}_K = \underbrace{(B^\dagger \delta_K)}_{=: \hat{\delta}_K} \cdot x.$$

Altogether the previous computations show that we can assume without loss of generality that the considered strict generalized response has as active area $A_K = \hat{A}_K$ with δ_K being perpendicular to the first unit vector and \mathbf{b}_K being zero.

We compare the performance of the response \mathcal{R} with the κ -indexed family of generalized responses $(\mathcal{R}^\kappa : \kappa \geq 1)$ of dimension d or smaller given by

$$(74) \quad \mathcal{R}^\kappa(x) = \mathbf{a}(x) + \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \mathbb{1}_{A_k}(x) (\delta_k \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_k) + \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x),$$

where

$$(75) \quad \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x) = \frac{1}{2}(\delta_K \cdot x + \kappa x_1)^+ - \frac{1}{2}(-\delta_K \cdot x + \kappa x_1)^+.$$

Let

$$(76) \quad \tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, y) = \mathcal{L}(x, \mathbf{a}(x) + \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} (\delta_k \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_k) \mathbb{1}_{A_k}(x) + y), \quad \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x) = \mathbb{1}_{A_K}(x) (\delta_K \cdot x),$$

$\delta'_K = (\delta_{K,2}, \dots, \delta_{K,d_{\text{in}}})^\dagger$ and similarly $x' = (x_2, \dots, x_{d_{\text{in}}})^\dagger$ and note that

$$(77) \quad \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x) = \begin{cases} \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x), & \text{if } \kappa|x_1| \geq |\delta'_K \cdot x'|, \\ \text{lin. interpol. of } \tilde{\mathcal{R}} \text{ between } \check{x}^{(\kappa)} \text{ and } \hat{x}^{(\kappa)}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where

$$(78) \quad \check{x}^{(\kappa)} = \left(-\frac{1}{\kappa} |\delta'_K \cdot x'| \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{x}^{(\kappa)} = \left(\frac{1}{\kappa} |\delta'_K \cdot x'| \right).$$

For $\varepsilon > 0$ denote by \mathcal{D}_ε the set

$$\mathcal{D}_\varepsilon = \left\{ x' \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}-1} : \begin{array}{l} \text{the segment } \left[\begin{pmatrix} -\varepsilon \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon \\ x' \end{pmatrix} \right] \text{ has distance greater or equal to } \varepsilon \text{ to every } \partial A_k \text{ (} k \neq K \text{)} \\ \text{and there exists } x_0 \in \mathbb{R} \text{ so that } (x_0, x') \in \mathbb{D} \end{array} \right\}$$

It is straight-forward to verify that \mathcal{D}_ε is closed and due to the compactness of \mathbb{D} also compact. Moreover,

$$(79) \quad \bigcup_{\varepsilon > 0} \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon = \underbrace{\{x' \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}-1} : [\exists x_0 \in \mathbb{R} : (x_0, x') \in \mathbb{D}] \text{ and } [\forall k \neq K : (0, x') \notin \partial A_k]\}}_{=: \mathcal{D}}.$$

We have

$$(80) \quad \begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{D}} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}^\kappa(x)) h(x) dx - \int_{\mathbb{D}} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x)) h(x) dx \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{D}} \tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x)) h(x) dx - \int_{\mathbb{D}} \tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x)) h(x) dx \\ &= \int_{D_\kappa} (\tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x)) - \tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x))) h(x) dx, \end{aligned}$$

where $D_\kappa = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x' \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : x' \in \mathcal{D}, |x_1| \leq \frac{1}{\kappa} |\delta'_K \cdot x'| \right\}$. In dependence on $\varepsilon > 0$ we partition D_κ in two sets

$$(81) \quad D'_{\kappa, \varepsilon} = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x' \end{pmatrix} \in D_\kappa : x' \in \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon \right\} \quad \text{and} \quad D''_{\kappa, \varepsilon} = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x' \end{pmatrix} \in D_\kappa : x' \in \mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon \right\}.$$

We note that $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}$ is continuous on $([-\varepsilon, \varepsilon] \times \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon) \times \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ as consequence of the continuity of \mathcal{L} (see Lemma 4.1) and the particular choice of \mathcal{D}_ε . Moreover, for sufficiently large κ (depending on ε), $D'_{\kappa, \varepsilon} \subseteq [-\varepsilon, \varepsilon] \times \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon$. Using that continuous functions are uniformly continuous on compacts, that h is uniformly bounded and the Lebesgue measure of D_κ is of order $\mathcal{O}(1/\kappa)$ we conclude that in terms of $\Upsilon_{x'} := |\delta'_K \cdot x'|$

$$(82) \quad \begin{aligned} & \int_{D'_{\kappa, \varepsilon}} (\tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x)) - \tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x))) h(x) dx \\ &= \int_{D'_{\kappa, \varepsilon}} \left(\tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x)\right) - \tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x)\right) \right) h\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right) dx + o\left(\frac{1}{\kappa}\right) \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{D}_\varepsilon} \left(\int_{-\frac{1}{\kappa} \Upsilon_{x'}}^{\frac{1}{\kappa} \Upsilon_{x'}} \left(\tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa\left(\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right)\right) - \tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right)\right) \right) dx_1 \right) h\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right) dx' + o\left(\frac{1}{\kappa}\right) \end{aligned}$$

as $\kappa \rightarrow \infty$. Moreover, for every $x' \in \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon$ one has

$$(83) \quad \begin{aligned} & \int_{-\frac{1}{\kappa} \Upsilon_{x'}}^{\frac{1}{\kappa} \Upsilon_{x'}} \left(\tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa\left(\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right)\right) - \tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right)\right) \right) dx_1 \\ &= \frac{1}{\kappa} \int_{-\Upsilon_{x'}}^{\Upsilon_{x'}} \left(\tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^1\left(\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right)\right) - \tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right)\right) \right) dx_1 =: \frac{1}{\kappa} Q(x'). \end{aligned}$$

We represent $Q(x')$ in terms of the measure $\nu_{x'} = \text{Leb}|_{[-\Upsilon_{x'}, \Upsilon_{x'}]}$, the strictly convex function

$$(84) \quad \xi_{x'}: [-\Upsilon_{x'}, \Upsilon_{x'}] \rightarrow [0, \infty), \quad x_1 \mapsto \tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^1\left(\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right)\right)$$

and its secant $\bar{\xi}_{x'}: [-\Upsilon_{x'}, \Upsilon_{x'}] \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ that equals $\xi_{x'}$ in the boundary points and is linear in between. One has

$$(85) \quad Q(x') = \int (\xi_{x'}(z) - \bar{\xi}_{x'}(z)) d\nu_{x'} \leq 0$$

with strict inequality in the case where $\Upsilon_{x'} > 0$ (due to strict convexity). Consequently, we get with (82) that

$$(86) \quad \lim_{\kappa \rightarrow \infty} \kappa \int_{D''_{\kappa, \varepsilon}} (\tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x)) - \tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x))) h(x) dx = \int_{\mathcal{D}_\varepsilon} Q(x') h\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right) dx'.$$

To analyze the contribution of the integrals on $D''_{\kappa, \varepsilon}$ we note that by uniform boundedness of $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x)) - \tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x))$ over all $x \in \mathbb{D}$ and $\kappa \geq 1$ one has existence of a constant C not depending on κ and ε such that

$$(87) \quad \left| \int_{D''_{\kappa, \varepsilon}} (\tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x)) - \tilde{\mathcal{L}}(x, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x))) h(x) dx \right| \leq C |\mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon| \frac{1}{\kappa},$$

where $|\mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon|$ is the $(d_{\text{in}} - 1)$ -dimensional Hausdorff measure of the set $\mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon$. By choosing $\varepsilon > 0$ arbitrarily small one can make $|\mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon|$ arbitrarily small and with a diagonalization argument we obtain with (80) and (86) that

$$(88) \quad \lim_{\kappa \rightarrow \infty} \kappa \int_{\mathbb{D}} (\mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}^\kappa(x)) - \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x))) h(x) dx = \int_{\mathcal{D}} Q(x') h\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right) dx'.$$

Now there exists $x' \in \mathcal{D}$ with $h(x') > 0$ and by continuity of h we can choose x' such that, additionally, $\Upsilon_{x'} = |\delta'_K \cdot x'| > 0$. By continuity we thus get that

$$(89) \quad \int_{\mathcal{D}} Q(x') h\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right) dx' < 0$$

and, consequently, there exists $\kappa > 0$ such that the generalized response \mathcal{R}^κ of dimension d or smaller has a strictly smaller error than \mathcal{R} . Hence, it has to be simple.

It remains to treat the case where δ_K and \mathbf{n}_K are linearly dependent. In that case we choose $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ with $\delta_K = \alpha \mathbf{n}_K$, we extend $\tau_1 = \mathbf{n}_K$ to an orthonormal basis $(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_{d_{\text{in}}})$ of $\mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ and denote by B the matrix formed by the vectors $\tau_1, \dots, \tau_{d_{\text{in}}}$. Moreover, choose $c = (o_K, 0, \dots, 0)^\dagger$ and set $\varphi(x) = B(x + c)$. Then the response $\hat{\mathcal{R}} = \mathcal{R} \circ \varphi$ has as K th activation area $\hat{A}_K = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : x_1 > 0\}$ and on \hat{A}_K the K th summand in the respective representation of $\hat{\mathcal{R}}$ is

$$(90) \quad \delta_K \cdot \varphi(x) + \mathbf{b}_K = \alpha(x_1 + o_K) + \mathbf{b}_K = \alpha x_1 + \hat{\mathbf{b}}_K,$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_K = \alpha o_K + \mathbf{b}_K \neq 0$ since otherwise we would have that

$$(91) \quad \partial A_K \subseteq \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} : \delta_K \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_K = 0\}.$$

We showed that in the remaining case we can assume without loss of generality that $A_K = \hat{A}_K$, $\delta_K = (\alpha, 0, \dots, 0)^\dagger$ for an $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathbf{b}_K \neq 0$.

In analogy to above we compare the response \mathcal{R} with the κ -indexed family of responses $(\mathcal{R}^\kappa : \kappa \geq 1)$ given by

$$(92) \quad \mathcal{R}^\kappa(x) = \mathbf{a}(x) + \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} (\delta_k \cdot x + \mathbf{b}_k) \mathbb{1}_{A_k}(x) + \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x),$$

where

$$(93) \quad \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x) = \frac{1}{2}(\alpha + \mathbf{b}_K \kappa) \left(x_1 + \frac{1}{\kappa}\right)^+ + \frac{1}{2}(\alpha - \mathbf{b}_K \kappa) \left(x_1 - \frac{1}{\kappa}\right)^+.$$

We use $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}$ as before, see (76), and note that $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa$ agrees with $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$ with $|x_1| \geq \frac{1}{\kappa}$. In analogy to above, we conclude that

$$(94) \quad \begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{D}} (\mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}^\kappa(x)) - \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x))) h(x) dx \\ &= \int_{D_\kappa} \left(\tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x)\right) - \tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x)\right) \right) h\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right) dx + o\left(\frac{1}{\kappa}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where $D_\kappa = [-\frac{1}{\kappa}, \frac{1}{\kappa}] \times \mathcal{D}$. As above we split the domain of integration into the two sets $D'_{\kappa, \varepsilon}$ and $D''_{\kappa, \varepsilon}$. Now in terms of

$$(95) \quad \xi_{x'} : [-1, 1] \rightarrow [0, \infty), \quad x_1 \mapsto \tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \frac{1}{2}(x_1 + 1)\mathbf{b}_K\right)$$

we get by using the uniform continuity of $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}$ on $D'_{\kappa, \varepsilon}$ and the fact that $|D_{\kappa, \varepsilon}| = \mathcal{O}(\frac{1}{\kappa})$ as $\kappa \rightarrow \infty$ that

$$(96) \quad \begin{aligned} & \int_{D'_{\kappa, \varepsilon}} \left(\tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}^\kappa(x)\right) - \tilde{\mathcal{L}}\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}, \tilde{\mathcal{R}}(x)\right) \right) h\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right) dx \\ &= \frac{1}{\kappa} \int_{\mathcal{D}_\varepsilon} \int_{-1}^1 \xi_{x'}(x_1) dx_1 - (\xi_{x'}(-1) + \xi_{x'}(1)) h\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right) dx' + o\left(\frac{1}{\kappa}\right). \end{aligned}$$

By strict convexity of $\xi_{x'}$, we get that $Q(x') := \int_{-1}^1 \xi_{x'}(x_1) dx_1 - (\xi_{x'}(-1) + \xi_{x'}(1)) < 0$. With the same arguments as in the first case one obtains that

$$(97) \quad \lim_{\kappa \rightarrow \infty} \kappa \int_{\mathbb{D}} (\mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}^\kappa(x)) - \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x))) h(x) dx = \int_{\mathcal{D}} Q(x') h\left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x' \end{pmatrix}\right) dx' < 0$$

so that there exists a response \mathcal{R}^κ with strictly smaller error than \mathcal{R} and the proof is finished. \square

Example 4.4. *If there exists a hyperplane H with $h(x) = 0$ for all $x \in H$ such that H intersects the convex hull of $\text{supp}(\mu)$ the conclusion of Theorem 1.2 is in general not true. Consider a continuous function $f : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that satisfies $f(x) = 1$ for all $x \in B((0, 1), 1)$ and $f(x) = 0$ for all $x \in B((1, -1), 1) \cup B((-1, -1), 1)$. Now, let $\mathcal{L}(x, y) = (f(x) - y)^2$ and μ be the measure on \mathbb{R}^2 with continuous Lebesgue density*

$$(98) \quad h(x) = \mathbb{1}_{B((0, 1), 1)}(x) |x - (0, 1)| + \mathbb{1}_{B((1, -1), 1)}(x) |x - (1, -1)| + \mathbb{1}_{B((-1, -1), 1)}(x) |x + (1, 1)|.$$

Then, we have $h(x) \equiv 0$ on $\mathbb{R} \times \{0\}$. Note that

$$(99) \quad \mathcal{R}(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x_2 \leq 0 \\ 1, & \text{if } x_2 > 0 \end{cases}$$

is a strict generalized response of dimension 2 with $\int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathcal{R}(x)) d\mu(x) = 0$. Conversely, there does not exist a network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ (for arbitrary $d \in \mathbb{N}$) with $\int \mathcal{L}(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x)) d\mu(x) = 0$. In particular, assume that there exist $d \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ with $\text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbb{W}) = 0$. Then, every breakline

FIGURE 1. Visualization of the minimization task in Example 4.4. There exists a generalized response of dimension 2 but no neural network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ ($d \in \mathbb{N}$) attaining zero error.

$H \neq \mathbb{R} \times \{0\}$ that intersects the interior of D contains an uncountable set of points $x \in H$ with $h(x) > 0$ and for all such points the function f is constant in a neighborhood of x . Therefore, the collective response of the neurons with breakline H has to be constant and we can without loss of generality assume that all ReLU neurons have the breakline $H = \mathbb{R} \times \{0\}$. Moreover, since $\text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbb{W}) = 0$ it holds that $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x) = 0$ for all $x = (x_1, x_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ with $x_2 < 0$ and $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x) = 1$ for all $x = (x_1, x_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ with $x_2 > 0$. This contradicts the continuity of $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}$.

Thus, there does not exist a global minimum in the loss landscape $\mathcal{W}_d \ni \mathbb{W} \rightarrow \text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbb{W})$ (for arbitrary $d \in \mathbb{N}$) and, in order to solve the minimization task iteratively, the sequence of networks returned by a gradient based algorithm have unbounded parameters.

For a thorough investigation of the non-existence of global minima in the approximation of discontinuous target functions f , see [GJL22].

Next, we show that in many situations if the class of network responses is not able to produce the function $x \mapsto \mathbf{m}(x)$ defined in Lemma 4.1 the minimal error strictly decreases after adding a ReLU neuron to the network structure.

Proposition 4.5. *Let $d \in \mathbb{N}_0$, assume that $\mathbb{D} = \text{supp}(\mu)$ is a compact set, assume there exists $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ with $\text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbb{W}) = \text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} < \infty$, assume for every $x \in \mathbb{D}$ that the function $\mathcal{L}(x, \cdot)$ is convex,*

- (i) *assume for every compact $K \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ there exists $L \in \mathbb{R}$ such that for all $x \in \mathbb{D}$, $y, y' \in K$ that*

$$(100) \quad |\mathcal{L}(x, y) - \mathcal{L}(x, y')| \leq L|y - y'|,$$

- (ii) *assume for every affine function $\varphi: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that the set*

$$(101) \quad \{x \in \mathbb{D}: \mathcal{L} \text{ is not } y\text{-differentiable in } (x, \varphi(x))\}$$

is a Lebesgue nullset,

and assume that there exist no neural network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ satisfying for μ -almost all $x \in \mathbb{D}$ that

$$(102) \quad \mathcal{L}(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x)) = \inf_{y \in \mathbb{R}} \mathcal{L}(x, y).$$

Then

$$(103) \quad \text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} > \text{err}_{d+1}^{\mathcal{L}}.$$

Remark 4.6. *We compare the assumptions of Proposition 4.5 with those of Theorem 1.2. In Proposition 4.5 we explicitly assume the existence of an optimal network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ and relax the continuity assumption on \mathcal{L} in the first component and the strict convexity assumption on \mathcal{L} in the second component. On the other hand, we introduce assumptions on the smoothness of \mathcal{L} in*

the second component. Under the assumptions of Theorem 1.2, condition (i) of Proposition 4.5 is satisfied (cf. [Roc70, Thm. 10.6]) and we can apply the latter proposition if additionally condition (ii) is satisfied. In that case, the statement of Proposition 4.5 can be rewritten as follows: if $\text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} \leq \text{err}_{d+1}^{\mathcal{L}}$, then there exists a neural network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ with $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x) = \mathbf{m}(x)$ for all $x \in \mathbb{D}$.

Proof of Proposition 4.5. Let $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_d$ be a network with $\text{err}^{\mathcal{L}}(\mathbb{W}) = \text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}}$. For $\Delta, o \in \mathbb{R}$, $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{S}^{d_{\text{in}}-1}$ consider the function

$$(104) \quad N(\Delta, \mathbf{n}, o)(x) = \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x) + \Delta(\mathbf{n} \cdot x - o)^+.$$

If $\text{err}_d^{\mathcal{L}} \leq \text{err}_{d+1}^{\mathcal{L}}$ then we have for all $\Delta, o \in \mathbb{R}$, $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{S}^{d_{\text{in}}-1}$ that

$$(105) \quad \int_{\mathbb{D}} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x)) h(x) dx \leq \int_{\mathbb{D}} \mathcal{L}(x, N(\Delta, \mathbf{n}, o)(x)) h(x) dx$$

and taking the derivative with respect to Δ at $\Delta = 0$ yields

$$(106) \quad \int_{\mathbb{D}} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x)) \right) (\mathbf{n} \cdot x - o)^+ h(x) dx = 0,$$

where $x \mapsto \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x))$ is uniformly bounded and well-defined outside a Lebesgue nullset. Indeed, since $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}$ is piecewise affine there exists a finite number of affine functions $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_m$ such that the set of points $x \in \mathbb{D}$ for which \mathcal{L} is not y -differentiable in $(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x))$ is contained in

$$(107) \quad \bigcup_{i=1}^m \{x \in \mathbb{D} : \mathcal{L} \text{ is not } y\text{-differentiable in } (x, \varphi_i(x))\},$$

which by (ii) is a nullset. Moreover, the boundedness of the derivative follows from the Lipschitz continuity of \mathcal{L} in the second argument, see (i). We let

$$(108) \quad \tilde{h}(x) := \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x)) \right) h(x)$$

and note that the space \mathcal{H} of all continuous functions $g: \mathbb{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ satisfying

$$(109) \quad \int_{\mathbb{D}} g(x) \tilde{h}(x) dx = 0$$

is linear and closed under convergence in $C(\mathbb{D}, \mathbb{C})$ (endowed with supremum norm). We showed that \mathcal{H} contains all functions of the form $x \mapsto (\mathbf{n} \cdot x - o)^+$ and it is standard to deduce that \mathcal{H} contains all polynomials and, using the Stone-Weierstrass theorem, thus all continuous functions. By the Riesz–Markov–Kakutani representation theorem, the measure $\tilde{h}(x) dx$ is the zero-measure and \tilde{h} is zero except for μ -nullsets. Note that $h > 0$, μ -almost everywhere, and hence $\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x)) = 0$, μ -almost everywhere. Using the convexity of $y \mapsto \mathcal{L}(x, y)$ we get $\mathcal{L}(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x)) = \inf_{y \in \mathbb{R}} \mathcal{L}(x, y)$, μ -almost everywhere. \square

In the next example, we show that the conclusion of Proposition 4.5 is in general false if condition (ii) is not satisfied. We note that the loss function \mathcal{L} in the example is not strictly convex but the statements of Lemma 4.1 still hold in this case.

Example 4.7. Consider the following regression problem. Let $d_{\text{in}} = 1$, $\ell \geq 1$, $\mu = \text{Leb}|_{[-\ell-1, 1+\ell]}$ be the Lebesgue measure on the interval $[-\ell-1, 1+\ell]$ and $\mathcal{L}(x, y) = |y - f(x)|$ where

$$(110) \quad f(x) = \begin{cases} 1 - |x|, & \text{if } |x| \leq 1 \\ 0, & \text{if } |x| > 1 \end{cases}.$$

FIGURE 2. Visualization of the minimization task in Example 4.7. There exists a network $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_3$ with $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}} = f$ (blue). However, the realization function attaining minimal error in the class \mathcal{W}_2 , \mathcal{W}_1 , and \mathcal{W}_0 is $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}} = 0$ (red).

Note that $\lambda(\{x \in [-\ell - 1, \ell + 1] : \mathcal{L} \text{ is not } y\text{-differentiable in } (x, 0)\}) = 2\ell > 0$ and

$$(111) \quad f(x) = (x + 1)^+ - 2(x)^+ + (x - 1)^+$$

so that f is the response of a network using three ReLU neurons and $\text{err}_3^{\mathcal{L}} = 0$. We show that for $\ell \geq 13$ we have

$$(112) \quad \text{err}_0^{\mathcal{L}} = \text{err}_1^{\mathcal{L}} = \text{err}_2^{\mathcal{L}} = \int_{-\ell-1}^{\ell+1} |f(x)| dx = 1,$$

i.e. the best regression function in the set of response functions for networks having 2 ReLU neurons is the zero function although $\inf_{y \in \mathbb{R}} \mathcal{L}(x, y) = f(x)$ is not the zero function. This shows that the conclusion of Proposition 4.5 is in general false if Assumption (ii) is not satisfied.

Denote by $E: \mathcal{W}_2 \times \mathbb{I} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the function

$$(113) \quad (\mathbb{W}, [s, t]) \mapsto E(\mathbb{W}, [s, t]) = \int_s^t |\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x) - f(x)| - |f(x)| dx,$$

where \mathbb{I} is the set of all closed intervals that are subsets of $[-\ell - 1, \ell + 1]$. We show that for $\ell \geq 13$ we have $E(\mathbb{W}, [-\ell - 1, 1 + \ell]) \geq 0$ for all networks $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_2$.

Let $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_2$. Then $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}$ is continuous and satisfies

$$(114) \quad \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x) = \begin{cases} \delta_1 x + \mathbf{b}_1, & \text{if } x \leq o_1 \\ \delta_2 x + \mathbf{b}_2, & \text{if } o_1 < x < o_2, \\ \delta_3 x + \mathbf{b}_3, & \text{if } x > o_2 \end{cases}$$

for $\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3, \mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2, \mathbf{b}_3, o_1, o_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ with $o_1 \leq o_2$.

First, we assume that $o_1 \leq 0 \leq o_2$ and $0 \leq \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)$. We fix $\delta_2, \mathbf{b}_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ and derive a lower bound for $E(\mathbb{W}, [0, \ell + 1])$ over all feasible choices of o_2, δ_3 and \mathbf{b}_3 . We start with the case $\delta_2 < 0$. Note that the choice $o_2 = \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/|\delta_2|$, $\delta_3 = \mathbf{b}_3 = 0$ yields a better result than all networks with $o_2 \geq \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/|\delta_2|$. Therefore we can restrict the optimization task to networks satisfying $o_2 \leq \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/|\delta_2|$. For $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/|\delta_2| \leq 1$ we show that, indeed, the optimal choice for the approximation of f on the right-hand side of the y -axis is $o_2 = \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/|\delta_2|$, $\delta_3 = \mathbf{b}_3 = 0$. If $o_2 < \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/|\delta_2|$ and $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(1) \leq 0$ then

$$(115) \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [o_2, a]) \geq -\frac{1}{2}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_2)(a - o_2) \quad \text{and} \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [a, \ell + 1]) \geq \frac{1}{2}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_2)(a - o_2),$$

where $a \in [0, 1]$ with $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(a) = 0$. Conversely, if $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(1) \geq 0$ then $E(\mathbb{W}, [o_2, 1]) \geq -\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_2)(1 - o_2) \geq -\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_2)$. We consider two cases. If $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(\ell + 1) \geq 0$ then $\delta_3 \geq -\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_2)/\ell$. Thus,

$E(\mathbb{W}, [1, \ell + 1]) \geq \frac{1}{2}\ell\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(1) \geq \frac{\ell-1}{2}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_2)$ so that for $\ell \geq 3$ we get $E(\mathbb{W}, [o_2, \ell + 1]) \geq 0$. If $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(\ell + 1) \leq 0$ then $\delta_3 \leq -\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_2)/(\ell + 1)$. In that case, $E(\mathbb{W}, [1, \ell + 1])$ corresponds to the area of two triangles with slope $|\delta_3|$ and baselines that add to ℓ . This is minimized by two congruent triangles so that

$$(116) \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [1, \ell + 1]) \geq \left(\frac{\ell}{2}\right)^2 |\delta_3| \geq \frac{\ell-1}{4}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_2).$$

Thus, for $\ell \geq 5$ we get $E(\mathbb{W}, [o_2, \ell + 1]) \geq 0$ and the optimal choice is $o_2 = \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/|\delta_2|$, $\delta_3 = \mathfrak{b}_3 = 0$.

It remains to consider the case $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/|\delta_2| \geq 1$. In this case the choice $\delta_3 > 0$ is clearly suboptimal and for $o_2 \leq 1$ we get $E(\mathbb{W}, [0, o_2]) \geq -(\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0) - \frac{1}{2}|\delta_2|)$. The above calculations show that

$$(117) \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [o_2, \ell + 1]) \geq \frac{\ell-5}{4}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_2) \geq \frac{\ell-5}{4}(\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0) - |\delta_2|)$$

so that for $\ell \geq 7$ we have $E(\mathbb{W}, [0, \ell + 1]) \geq -\frac{1}{2}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)$. If $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/|\delta_2| \geq \ell + 1$ the choice $o_2 > 1$ is suboptimal and in the case $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/|\delta_2| \leq \ell + 1$ where $o_2 \leq 1$ is not the optimal choice it is easy to see that actually $o_2 = \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/|\delta_2|$, $\delta_3 = \mathfrak{b}_3 = 0$ is the best choice. In that case

$$(118) \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [0, 1]) \geq -(\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0) - \frac{1}{2}|\delta_2|) \quad \text{and} \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [1, \ell + 1]) \geq \frac{1}{2}(\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0) - |\delta_2|).$$

In conclusion, in all of the above cases we get for $\ell \geq 7$ that $E(\mathbb{W}, [0, \ell + 1]) \geq -\frac{1}{2}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)$.

Next, we consider the case $\delta_2 \geq 0$. Set $a := \inf\{x \geq 0: \delta_2 x + \mathfrak{b}_2 \geq 1 - x\}$. Choosing $o_2 > a$ or $\delta_3 \geq 0$ is clearly suboptimal. For $0 \leq o_2 \leq a$ and $\delta_3 < 0$ note that $E(\mathbb{W}, [0, 1]) \geq -\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_2)$. Analogously to the case $\delta_2 < 0$ we get

$$(119) \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [1, \ell + 1]) \geq \frac{\ell-1}{4}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_2)$$

so that for $\ell \geq 7$

$$(120) \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [0, \ell + 1]) \geq \frac{1}{2}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_2) \geq \frac{1}{2}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0).$$

Now, if $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0) \leq 0$ and $\ell \geq 5$ then the above calculations imply that $E(\mathbb{W}, [-\ell - 1, \ell + 1]) \geq 0$. Using the symmetry of the problem we showed that for all networks $\mathbb{W} \in \mathcal{W}_2$ satisfying $o_1 \leq 0 \leq o_2$ we have that

$$(121) \quad \int_{-\ell-1}^{\ell+1} \mathcal{L}(x, \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(x)) dx \geq \int_{-\ell-1}^{\ell+1} \mathcal{L}(x, 0) dx.$$

Using again the symmetry, we are therefore left with considering the case $0 < o_1 \leq o_2$. We can clearly focus on the case $o_1 \leq 1$ and $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0) \geq 0$. Note that one can use the above arguments in order to show that

$$(122) \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [o_1, \ell + 1]) \geq \min(0, -\frac{1}{2}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(o_1)).$$

If $\delta_1 < 0$ we thus get

$$(123) \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [0, \ell + 1]) \geq -\frac{3}{2}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0).$$

On the other hand, $E(\mathbb{W}, [-\ell - 1, 0]) \geq (\ell - 1)\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)$ so that, for $\ell \geq 5/2$, we have $E(\mathbb{W}, [-\ell - 1, \ell + 1]) \geq 0$. Conversely, if $\delta_1 \geq 0$ we get

$$(124) \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [0, \ell + 1]) \geq -\frac{3}{2}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0) - \delta_1$$

and for $\delta_1 \geq \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)$ and $\ell \geq 9/2$ we clearly have $E(\mathbb{W}, [-\ell - 1, \ell + 1]) \geq 0$. For $\delta_1 \leq \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)$ we get

$$(125) \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [-1, \ell + 1]) \geq -\frac{5}{2}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0) - \frac{1}{2}\delta_1.$$

Now for $\delta_1 \leq \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/(\ell + 1)$ we get

$$(126) \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [-\ell - 1, -1]) \geq \frac{1}{2}\ell\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(1) \geq \frac{1}{2}(\ell - 1)\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)$$

and for $\ell \geq 7$ we get that $E(\mathbb{W}, [-\ell - 1, \ell + 1]) \geq 0$. If $\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)/(\ell + 1) \leq \delta_1 \leq \mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0)$ then

$$(127) \quad E(\mathbb{W}, [-\ell - 1, -1]) \geq \left(\frac{\ell}{2}\right)^2 |\delta_1| \geq \frac{\ell - 1}{4}\mathfrak{N}^{\mathbb{W}}(0).$$

Thus, if $\ell \geq 13$ have $E(\mathbb{W}, [-\ell - 1, \ell + 1]) \geq 0$ and the proof of the assertion is finished.

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